

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEMS OF TOURISM IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The given article deals with a brief comparative analysis of the English and Uzbek terminology system of the tourism field. According to the structure of terms, their performance in the process of generating terms and terminology systems is analyzed and disclosed. The difficulties encountered at the initial stage of the study of tourism terminology indicate a lack of glossary in the field of tourism.*

Keywords: *terminology, tourism, term, structure, component, model.*

Introduction:

Linguistic and cultural studies of terms open up opportunities for the study of many areas. Consideration of terms and their term systems in the aspect of linguoculturology allows you to look at them from several sides and attract more different information for research. "In world linguistics, a great place is given to the study of linguistic and non-linguistic factors necessary for the socio-cultural, economic and political ties of each nation with fraternal peoples, the solution of such priority issues as the formation of the terminology language of various industries and specialties" Among a wide thematic range of terms in the Russian and Uzbek languages in the XXI century, the interest of researchers in tourism sector. This is due to social, political and cultural changes in the world. The growth of globalization contributes to the increase in interethnic communication both in the Internet format and in real life. V.S. Senin writes about the important role of tourism in the modern world in the Introduction to his dictionary: "In many countries, tourism plays a significant role in the formation of the gross domestic product, the creation of additional jobs and employment of the population, the activation of the foreign trade balance. Tourism has a huge impact on such key sectors of the economy as transport and communications, construction, agriculture, production of consumer goods and others, i.e. it acts as a kind of catalyst for socio-economic development. In turn, the development of tourism is influenced by various factors: demographic, natural geographic, socio-economic, historical, religious and political-legal" This topic has gained the greatest popularity and demand in the West, where the following definitions of the term "tourism" were given. Let's compare, Jafara Jafari: "Tourism is the study of a person who is outside the territory of his permanent residence, the industry that meets his needs, and the effects that both a person and an industry have on the socio-cultural, economic and physical environment." Alister Matheson and Jeffrey Wall believe that: "Tourism is the temporary movement of people to destinations outside of their usual places of employment and residence, the activities they engage in during their stay in these destinations, and infrastructure facilities created to meet their needs." "Since the second half of the XX century, the world linguistics has been expanding the range of studies of terminology of various branches, treating linguistic and cultural issues of their borrowing from other languages"

MAIN PART

The study in the field of tourist texts is divided into several areas: "The analysis of the theory of the issue allows us to identify three main areas of research in this area: terminological (research of the features of tourist terminology); lexicographic (reflection of tourist vocabulary in explanatory and bilingual dictionaries, compilation of special dictionaries of tourist terms); discursive (analysis of the features of tourist discourse on the example of tourist reference books, prospectuses, etc.)". Consequently, synonymy of terms is a phenomenon found in all languages of the world. Tourist with 334 synonyms in English and 144 interchangeable in Russian, the presence of terms has been established. Synonyms prevail in both languages. Synonym-the meaning partially coincides, but in terminology-synonyms that serve to express exactly the same concept. For example, in English at the same time as the term *adminstor* (administrator), he also expressed the term *receptionist* used to denote. In Uzbek, which means "recipient" literally means (in Uzbek, this is a variant of the term administrator is actively used for food).

DISCUSSION

The tourist terminosystem includes industry terms and terminoids the recipient is written as a system. The term "researcher" refers to professional special lexical units (professionalism), in professional colloquial speech (professionalnie prostorechie) and professional refers to jargon (professional jargon). At this stage, the term and professional vocabulary differ. Many researchers (M.N.Volodina, S.G.Kazarina) that these two layers of vocabulary coexist and although they note that they are on the same territory on an informational scale, some (N.M.Shansky) assess the professional lexicon as a term, while others (T.R.Kiyak) consider synonymous terms.

Thus, the terminological system of the tourism industry in recent years has increasingly become the focus of attention due to the rapid development of this branch of human activity. The main directions of research in the field of industry terminology are:

- 1) lexicographic terminological activity;
- 2) unification of terms and term systems, implying the ordering, standardization and harmonization of terms, the editor's work on terms (terminological editing);
- 3) translation of terms in scientific, technical and other special texts;
- 4) creation of terminological data banks or terminological databases;
- 5) organizational and methodological activities of terminological institutes and centers at different levels - from industry to international".

The system of terms related to tourism is not well studied. They can be proved by the following examples. There are many examples in Russian of tourism terminology, for example: surcharge for one stay - joy uchun qo'shimcha to'lov, visa application – visa olish uchun ariza. They are part of the terminology and consist mainly of common words found expressions. This suggests that it is terminology with a common vocabulary related. After all, tourist texts are intended not only for specialists in the field of tourism, but also for ordinary consumers in the outflow zone.

Due to the fact that there are few real tourist terms in Uzbek tourist dictionaries, the assimilation and adaptation of terms from languages (mainly Russian) is noticeable. For example: travel agency - sayyohlik agentligi; reception-qabulxona; family hotel-oilaviy mehmonxona; cooperation of guides-gid hamkorligi; transit(transportation of passengers from one country to another through an intermediate country)-yo'lovchilarni bir mamlakatdan ikkinchisiga oraliq mamlakat orqali olib o'tish; passenger ticket-yolovchi taloni; direct flight- togri togri uchish. In the course of scientific research, the predominance of multicomponent terms among tourist terms

has been revealed. The fact that it consists of complex phrases indicates its recent appearance relative to lexical units in the studied thematic group. Multicomponent terms have a complex semantic-structural formation consisting of various combinations of their components and consists of (Single-double-triple-quadruple room) a room with one, two, three and four bedrooms-bir ikki uch to'rt kishilik yotoqli xona; luggage storage-yuklarni nazorat qilish xonasi; non-refundable ticket-puli qaytarilmaydigan chipta; luggage storage room-yuk saqlash xonasi; residence permits-doimiy yashash uchun ruxsatnoma; customs formalities-bojxona rasmiyatchiligi; tourist bus-turistik avtobus. Difficulties may arise in translating multicomponent terms due to semantic and syntactic inconsistencies in the structures of the Russian and Uzbek languages.

METHODS

Considering that the tourism industry and its terminological system are in the development stage, the corpus of words that make up the vocabulary used in this area is increasing.

The enrichment of the dictionary of tourist terms is carried out in the following ways:

1) through work on mastering other languages. For example, borrowed from Russian into Uzbek;

2) using affixes and morphemes. This way of forming tourist terms is most often found in English. For example, the expression "ticket registration" in Uzbek can be translated by the term "ticketing", consisting of one word.

3) by combining the words into a hovercraft hovercraft, the leasing holder is the lessee;

4) the fourth way is the most common, most tourist terms consist of phrases. Thus, in the terminological system of tourism, a larger layer is occupied not by one word, but by multicomponent terms:

In turn, international terms, which are very common in the field of international tourism, greatly facilitate the process of translating multicomponent terms: Full House* - the term means 100% hotel occupancy (all rooms are sold out)- barcha nomerlar band qilingani; Front Desk (front desk) - the reception desk of the hotel where guests register.

In the field of tourism, there are more polylex terms, they are used less often than simple one-component terms. Terms with several lexemes denote the basic concepts of this area (journey-sayohat, pilgrimage-ziyosat route-yo'nalish; instructor-yo'l boshlovchi; resort-dam olish maskani; transport-/transport xizmati; flight-parvoz. The analysis of tourist terms shows that in their structure and form, most terms in the Russian language have a substantive model. Among the analyzed Russian terms, two-component terms with a meaningful model prevail: hotel chain-mehmonxona tarmog'i; (party ticket) group ticket-guruh chiptasi, (passenger handling) passenger service - yo'lovchilarga xizmat; The most common terms in the Uzbek language are expressions. Among the polylexemic terms, the adjective-essential model prevails (tourism industry, hotel complex, sightseeing tourism, off-season). The study showed that the most common complex terms are (a lyuks, lyuks kvartira, wagon bufet, gid hamrohligi, navigator) va qisqartmalar yordamida tuzilgan atamalar (turoperator, ekoturizm, parvoz, sayyohlik agentligi, turagent). Etymological research makes it possible to determine from which word certain terms originate, and to determine which model of word formation is used.

The tasks of etymology include determining the ways of developing and replenishing the vocabulary of the language. Therefore, it is necessary to determine which models are used to create lexical units. Since the tourist terminology is replete with multicomponent terms and prepositions, it can be said that the syntactic way of term formation prevails in the studied

languages. It can be assumed that professional-level ties in the field of tourism in Uzbekistan were quite effective, since interethnic ties contributed to the consolidation of a huge number of borrowed lexemes in the language

CONCLUSION

As part of the study, the following were identified:

1. Tourist terms in Russian and Uzbek languages in this terminological system of tourist activity and concepts in the field of tourism correspond to the conceptual terminological field, the micropole and it is divided into thematic groups.

2. The formation of the tourism terminological system differs in the Russian and Uzbek languages of the past. The terminology of tourism in English is almost firmly established, in Russian and in the language-a developing system.

3. The maximum affinity in the terminology of bilingual tourism, the term harvest in the presence of a participle is observed on a morphemic basis. The term of education productive method is suffixation and compound word formation for both languages.

4. The big difference in the terminology of tourism in Russian and English seems to be at the level of skill. The term is mastered in Russian by 60.3%, in Uzbek - and in the language -6.3%. Hence the borrowing of the term Russian in the language is a productive method. The plural of Uzbek borrowings of bilingual term systems indicate a tendency towards mutual convergence.

To the comparative analysis of tourist terms in Russian and Uzbek, scientific and theoretical in this research work devoted to the study of formal-structural and mathematical methods of statistics were widely used.

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